

Supplementary Material

Relationship between Obstructive Sleep Apnea and Chronic Pain:
A Systematic Review on the Impact of OSA Treatment on Pain Outcomes

PROSPERO Registration: CRD420251007908

Appendix 1: Complete Search Strategies for All Databases

Database	Search String	Filters Applied	Results
PubMed (MEDLINE) Date: July 20, 2025	<pre> (("sleep apnea, obstructive"[MeSH Terms] OR "obstructive sleep apnea"[Title/Abstract] OR "obstructive sleep apnoea"[Title/Abstract] OR OSA[Title/Abstract] OR "sleep apnea syndrome"[Title/Abstract] OR "sleep apnoea syndrome"[Title/Abstract] OR "obstructive sleep apnea syndrome"[Title/Abstract] OR OSAS[Title/Abstract] OR "sleep disordered breathing"[Title/Abstract] OR "sleep-disordered breathing"[Title/Abstract])) AND (("chronic pain"[MeSH Terms] OR "pain"[MeSH Terms] OR "chronic pain"[Title/Abstract] OR "persistent pain"[Title/Abstract] OR "pain, chronic"[Title/Abstract] OR "musculoskeletal pain"[Title/Abstract] OR headache[Title/Abstract] OR "temporomandibular disorder"[Title/Abstract] OR "temporomandibular disorders"[Title/Abstract] OR TMD[Title/Abstract] OR fibromyalgia[Title/Abstract] OR "back pain"[Title/Abstract] OR "neck pain"[Title/Abstract] OR arthralgia[Title/Abstract] OR myalgia[Title/Abstract])) AND (("continuous positive airway pressure"[MeSH Terms] OR CPAP[Title/Abstract] OR "continuous positive airway pressure"[Title/Abstract] OR "mandibular advancement"[Title/Abstract] OR "mandibular advancement device"[Title/Abstract] OR MAD[Title/Abstract] OR "oral appliance"[Title/Abstract] OR "oral appliances"[Title/Abstract] OR "dental appliance"[Title/Abstract] OR "sleep apnea therapy"[Title/Abstract] OR "sleep apnoea therapy"[Title/Abstract] OR "positive airway pressure"[Title/Abstract] OR PAP[Title/Abstract] OR "upper airway surgery"[Title/Abstract] OR UPPP[Title/Abstract] OR uvulopalatopharyngoplasty[Title/Abstract] OR "positional therapy"[Title/Abstract])) </pre>	None (All years, all languages initially; language restriction applied during screening)	1,247
Scopus Date: July 20, 2025	<pre> TITLE-ABS-KEY(("obstructive sleep apnea" OR "obstructive sleep apnoea" OR osa OR "sleep apnea syndrome" OR "sleep apnoea syndrome" OR "obstructive sleep apnea syndrome" OR osas OR "sleep disordered breathing" OR "sleep-disordered breathing")) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY(("chronic pain" OR "persistent pain" OR "pain, chronic" OR "musculoskeletal pain" OR headache OR "temporomandibular disorder" OR "temporomandibular disorders" OR tmd OR fibromyalgia OR "back pain" OR "neck pain" OR arthralgia OR myalgia)) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY((cpap OR "continuous positive airway pressure" OR "mandibular advancement" OR "mandibular advancement device" OR mad OR "oral appliance" OR "oral appliances" OR "dental appliance" OR "sleep apnea therapy" OR "sleep apnoea therapy" OR "positive airway pressure" OR pap OR </pre>	None (All years, all languages initially; restrictions during screening)	856

	"upper airway surgery" OR uppp OR uvulopalatopharyngoplasty OR "positional therapy"))		
Web of Science Core Collection Date: July 20, 2025	TS=(("obstructive sleep apnea" OR "obstructive sleep apnoea" OR OSA OR "sleep apnea syndrome" OR "sleep apnoea syndrome" OR "obstructive sleep apnea syndrome" OR OSAS OR "sleep disordered breathing" OR "sleep-disordered breathing")) AND TS=(("chronic pain" OR "persistent pain" OR "pain, chronic" OR "musculoskeletal pain" OR headache OR "temporomandibular disorder" OR "temporomandibular disorders" OR TMD OR fibromyalgia OR "back pain" OR "neck pain" OR arthralgia OR myalgia)) AND TS=((CPAP OR "continuous positive airway pressure" OR "mandibular advancement" OR "mandibular advancement device" OR MAD OR "oral appliance" OR "oral appliances" OR "dental appliance" OR "sleep apnea therapy" OR "sleep apnoea therapy" OR "positive airway pressure" OR PAP OR "upper airway surgery" OR UPPP OR uvulopalatopharyngoplasty OR "positional therapy"))	None (All years, all document types, all languages initially)	342
Cochrane CENTRAL Date: July 20, 2025	#1 MeSH descriptor: [Sleep Apnea, Obstructive] explode all trees #2 ("obstructive sleep apnea" OR "obstructive sleep apnoea" OR OSA OR "sleep apnea syndrome" OR "sleep apnoea syndrome" OR OSAS OR "sleep disordered breathing"):ti,ab,kw #3 #1 OR #2 #4 MeSH descriptor: [Chronic Pain] explode all trees #5 ("chronic pain" OR "persistent pain" OR "musculoskeletal pain" OR headache OR "temporomandibular disorder" OR TMD OR fibromyalgia):ti,ab,kw #6 #4 OR #5 #7 MeSH descriptor: [Continuous Positive Airway Pressure] explode all trees #8 (CPAP OR "continuous positive airway pressure" OR "mandibular advancement" OR "oral appliance" OR MAD OR "sleep apnea therapy"):ti,ab,kw #9 #7 OR #8 #10 #3 AND #6 AND #9	Trials (Limited to controlled trials)	144
Additional Sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reference lists of included studies and relevant systematic reviews • ClinicalTrials.gov: 'obstructive sleep apnea AND chronic pain' • WHO ICTRP: Similar search terms • ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global • Author contact for additional data 	Hand-searching and grey literature	—
TOTAL RECORDS	Combined across all databases	—	2,589

Appendix 2: Detailed Data Extraction Form and Variables

Category	Data Field	Definition / Instructions
1. Study Identification	Study ID	Unique identifier assigned by reviewers
	First Author	Surname, Initials
	Publication Year	YYYY
	Journal/Source	Full journal name or source
	DOI/URL	Digital Object Identifier or web address
	Country	Country where study conducted
	Language	English / Spanish / Portuguese
2. Study Design and Methods	Study Design	RCT / Prospective Cohort / Before-After / Other
	Setting	Single-center / Multi-center / Community / Hospital-based
	Study Duration	Total duration from enrollment to final follow-up
	Recruitment Period	Start date - End date
	Funding Source	Industry / Government / Institution / None / Not reported
	Conflicts of Interest	Yes / No / Not reported - specify if yes
3. Participant Characteristics	Sample Size	Total N enrolled / N analyzed
	Age	Mean \pm SD or Median (IQR) or Range
	Sex Distribution	% Male / % Female / Number of each
	BMI	Mean \pm SD or Median (IQR)
	Comorbidities	List relevant comorbidities with prevalence
	Inclusion Criteria	List all inclusion criteria as stated
	Exclusion Criteria	List all exclusion criteria as stated
4. OSA Characteristics	Diagnostic Method	In-laboratory PSG / Home sleep apnea test / Other
	Baseline AHI	Mean \pm SD or Median (IQR) - events/hour
	OSA Severity	Mild (5-15) / Moderate (15-30) / Severe (>30) - % in each
	Oxygen Desaturation Index	Mean \pm SD or Median (IQR) if reported
	Minimum O2 Saturation	Mean \pm SD or Median (IQR) if reported
	Arousal Index	Mean \pm SD or Median (IQR) if reported
	Sleep Efficiency	Mean \pm SD or Median (IQR) if reported
5. Pain Characteristics	Pain Condition/Diagnosis	Specific diagnosis: TMD, fibromyalgia, headache type, etc.
	Pain Duration	Mean \pm SD or Median (IQR) in months/years
	Pain Location	Anatomical location(s)
	Pain Assessment Instruments	List all validated instruments - VAS, NRS, BPI, SF-MPQ, MIDAS, etc.
	Baseline Pain Intensity	Mean \pm SD or Median (IQR) for each scale used
	Pain Frequency	Episodes per week/month if applicable
	Pain-Related Disability	Functional impact scores if reported
	Current Pain Medications	List medications and dosages
6. Intervention Details	Intervention Type	CPAP / MAD / Surgery / Positional therapy / Other
	Intervention Details	CPAP: device, pressure, mask; MAD: type, titration, advancement; Surgery: type, details
	Intervention Duration	Duration of treatment in weeks/months
	Adherence Definition	How adherence defined - e.g., ≥ 4 hours/night, $\geq 70\%$ nights
	Adherence Measurement	Method of monitoring - objective/subjective
	Adherence Rate	% adherent patients or mean hours/night

	Co-interventions	Any additional treatments provided
	Adverse Events	List all adverse events related to intervention
7. Comparator Details	Comparator Type	Pre-treatment baseline / Sham device / Control group / Non-adherent
	Comparator Details	Specific details about control/comparison
	Sample Size in Comparator	N in control/comparison group
8. Outcome Measures	Primary Outcome	As defined by study authors
	Secondary Outcomes	List all secondary outcomes
	Follow-up Time Points	All assessment times: baseline, X weeks, X months, etc.
	Baseline Pain Score	Mean \pm SD or Median (IQR)
	Post-Intervention Pain Score	Mean \pm SD or Median (IQR)
	Change Score	Mean \pm SD or Median (IQR)
	Statistical Significance	P-value and effect size (Cohen's d) if calculable
	Response Rate	% achieving clinically meaningful improvement if reported
9. Post-Intervention OSA Parameters	Post-Treatment AHI	Mean \pm SD or Median (IQR) if reported
	Treatment Success Rate	% achieving AHI reduction criteria
	Sleep Quality Changes	PSQI or other sleep quality measures if reported
10. Additional Data	Dropouts/Loss to Follow-up	N and % with reasons
	Missing Data	Description of missing data and how handled
	Statistical Analysis	Statistical methods used
	Author Contact	Whether authors contacted / response received
	Reviewer Notes	Any additional notes or concerns

Appendix 3: PRISMA 2020 Checklist

Section/Topic	#	Checklist Item	Location in Manuscript
TITLE	1	Identify the report as a systematic review	Title page
ABSTRACT	2	See PRISMA 2020 for Abstracts checklist	Abstract
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in context of existing knowledge	Introduction, paragraphs 1-3
Objectives	4	Provide explicit statement of all objectives or questions	Introduction, final paragraph; Methods 2.2
Eligibility criteria	5	Specify inclusion and exclusion criteria and how studies grouped	Methods 2.2; Table 1
Information sources	6	Specify all databases, registers, websites, organizations searched	Methods 2.3; Appendix 1
Search strategy	7	Present full search strategies for all databases with filters/limits	Methods 2.4; Appendix 1
Selection process	8	Specify methods to decide study inclusion	Methods 2.5; Figure 1
Data collection	9	Specify methods to collect data and how many reviewers	Methods 2.6; Appendix 2
Data items	10a	List and define all outcomes sought	Methods 2.7, 2.9; Appendix 2
	10b	List and define all other variables sought	Methods 2.7; Appendix 2
Risk of bias	11	Specify methods to assess risk of bias	Methods 2.8; Results 3.3; Table 3; Figure 2
Effect measures	12	Specify effect measure(s) for each outcome	Methods 2.9
Synthesis methods	13a	Describe processes to decide study eligibility for synthesis	Methods 2.10
	13b	Describe methods to prepare data for synthesis	Methods 2.10
	13c	Describe methods to tabulate or display results	Methods 2.10; Tables 2-5
	13d	Describe methods to synthesize results and rationale	Methods 2.10; narrative synthesis
	13e	Describe methods to explore heterogeneity	Methods 2.10; Results 3.5
	13f	Describe sensitivity analyses	N/A - insufficient studies
Reporting bias	14	Describe methods to assess risk of bias from missing results	Methods 2.11; Results 3.6
Certainty	15	Describe methods to assess certainty of evidence	Methods 2.12; Results 3.7; Table 5; Appendix 4
Study selection	16a	Describe search and selection results	Results 3.1; Figure 1
	16b	Cite excluded studies and reasons	Results 3.1; Figure 1
Study characteristics	17	Cite each study and present characteristics	Results 3.2; Table 2; Appendix 6
Risk of bias	18	Present risk of bias assessments	Results 3.3; Table 3; Figure 2; Appendix 6
Individual studies	19	For each outcome, present summary statistics and effect estimates	Results 3.4; Table 4
Syntheses	20a	Summarize characteristics and risk of bias	Results 3.5
	20b	Present results of all syntheses	Results 3.5; Table 4
	20c	Present investigations of heterogeneity	Results 3.5
	20d	Present sensitivity analyses	N/A - insufficient studies
Reporting biases	21	Present assessments of reporting bias	Results 3.6
Certainty	22	Present certainty assessments for each outcome	Results 3.7; Table 5; Appendix 4
Discussion	23a	Interpret results in context of other evidence	Discussion, paragraphs 1-2
	23b	Discuss limitations of evidence	Discussion - Limitations
	23c	Discuss limitations of review processes	Discussion - Limitations
	23d	Discuss implications for practice, policy, research	Discussion - Clinical Implications; Future Research; Conclusions

Registration	24a	Provide registration information	Abstract; Methods 2.1; PROSPERO CRD420251007908
Protocol	24b	Indicate where protocol can be accessed	Methods 2.1; Data Availability
Amendments	24c	Describe amendments to protocol	No amendments made
Support	25	Describe funding sources and role	Funding; Acknowledgements
Competing interests	26	Declare competing interests	Conflicts of Interest
Data availability	27	Report availability of data, code, materials	Data Availability; All appendices available

Appendix 4: Detailed GRADE Evidence Profiles for All Outcomes

4.1 Morning Headache Improvement with CPAP

Component	Details
Question	Does CPAP treatment improve morning headache in adults with OSA?
Population	Adults with OSA and morning headache
Intervention	CPAP therapy (≥ 4 h/night, $\geq 70\%$ nights, ≥ 2 months)
Comparison	Pre-treatment baseline
Outcome	Morning headache improvement assessed by ICHD-3 beta criteria
Studies	1 study (Suzuki et al. 2015)
Design	Before-after observational study
Participants	N=235
Effect	81.3% improvement rate ($p < 0.001$)
Risk of Bias	Serious (-1): Uncontrolled design, no control group, selection bias, performance bias from unblinded intervention
Inconsistency	Not downgraded (0): Only one study, cannot assess consistency
Indirectness	Not downgraded (0): Direct evidence for target population and outcome
Imprecision	Serious (-1): Single study, confidence intervals not reported, cannot exclude alternative effects
Publication Bias	Not assessed: Too few studies
Overall Certainty	⊕⊕○○ LOW (Started at Low [observational], -1 risk of bias, -1 imprecision)

4.2 Temporomandibular Disorder Pain Reduction

Component	Details
Question	Does OSA treatment reduce temporomandibular disorder pain?
Population	Adults with OSA and TMD
Intervention	CPAP, MAD, or surgery for 18 months
Comparison	Untreated patients
Outcome	TMD pain intensity measured by DC/TMD CPI scale
Studies	1 study (Alessandri-Bonetti et al. 2024)
Design	Prospective cohort
Participants	N=40 (33 treated, 7 untreated)
Effect	Cohen's d = 0.8 favoring treatment ($p < 0.05$)
Risk of Bias	Serious (-1): Non-randomized, small control group (n=7), confounding by indication, no blinding
Inconsistency	Not downgraded (0): Only one study
Indirectness	Serious (-1): Multiple interventions pooled, effect may vary by type, 18-month follow-up may not reflect immediate effects
Imprecision	Not downgraded (0): Moderate effect size (0.8), statistically significant, clinically meaningful
Publication Bias	Not assessed: Too few studies
Overall Certainty	⊕⊕○○ LOW (Started at Low [observational], -1 risk of bias, -1 indirectness)

4.3 Primary Headache Improvement with MAD

Component	Details
Question	Does mandibular advancement device treatment improve primary headache?
Population	Adults with OSA and primary headache
Intervention	Mandibular advancement device
Comparison	Pre-treatment baseline
Outcome	Headache frequency and intensity (MIDAS, VAS)
Studies	1 study (Park et al. 2021)
Design	Prospective cohort
Participants	N=13
Effect	62% with $\geq 30\%$ frequency reduction; 23% with $\geq 50\%$ intensity reduction

Risk of Bias	Serious (-1): Uncontrolled design, no comparator, retrospective data collection, recall bias
Inconsistency	Not downgraded (0): Only one study
Indirectness	Not downgraded (0): Direct evidence for primary headache population
Imprecision	Very Serious (-2): Very small sample (n=13), wide confidence intervals likely, cannot exclude important benefit or harm
Publication Bias	Not assessed: Too few studies
Overall Certainty	⊕○○○ VERY LOW (Started at Low [observational], -1 risk of bias, -2 imprecision)

4.4 Generalized Chronic Pain Reduction with CPAP

Component	Details
Question	Does CPAP treatment reduce generalized chronic pain?
Population	Adults with moderate-to-severe OSA and chronic generalized pain
Intervention	CPAP therapy - adherent group ($\geq 4\text{h/night}$, $\geq 70\%$ nights)
Comparison	Non-adherent group
Outcome	Pain intensity (SF-MPQ PRI, VAS, BPI)
Studies	1 study (Shen et al. 2023)
Design	Prospective controlled study
Participants	N=80 (adherent vs non-adherent)
Effect	Cohen's d = 1.2 favoring adherent group ($p < 0.001$)
Risk of Bias	Serious (-1): Non-randomized adherence comparison, confounding by adherence characteristics, selection bias, no blinding
Inconsistency	Not downgraded (0): Only one study
Indirectness	Serious (-1): Adherence-based comparison rather than randomized assignment, effects may reflect adherence characteristics, moderate-to-severe OSA only
Imprecision	Not downgraded (0): Large effect size (1.2), statistically significant, clinically meaningful
Publication Bias	Not assessed: Too few studies
Overall Certainty	⊕⊕○○ LOW (Started at Low [observational], -1 risk of bias, -1 indirectness)

4.5 Multiple Sclerosis-Related Pain with CPAP

Component	Details
Question	Does CPAP treatment reduce MS-related pain?
Population	Adults with multiple sclerosis and non-severe OSA
Intervention	Fixed CPAP therapy
Comparison	Sham CPAP
Outcome	Pain score (VAS)
Studies	1 study (Khadadah et al. 2022)
Design	Randomized controlled trial (double-blind)
Participants	N=34 completers (49 randomized)
Effect	No significant difference; Cohen's d = 0.2 ($p = 0.64$)
Risk of Bias	Not downgraded (0): Well-conducted RCT, adequate randomization, double-blind, sham control
Inconsistency	Not downgraded (0): Only one study, consistent null finding
Indirectness	Not downgraded (0): Direct comparison in MS population (note: MS patients may differ from general chronic pain populations)
Imprecision	Serious (-1): Small sample (n=34), CIs not reported but likely wide, cannot exclude clinically important effect
Publication Bias	Not assessed: Too few studies (registered trial with published null results reduces concern)
Overall Certainty	⊕⊕⊕○ MODERATE (Started at High [RCT], -1 imprecision)

4.6 Fibromyalgia Pain with CPAP

Component	Details
Question	Does CPAP treatment reduce fibromyalgia pain?
Population	Female adults with fibromyalgia and OSA
Intervention	CPAP therapy
Comparison	Pre-treatment baseline (adherent subgroup)
Outcome	Pain scores (SIQR, VAS, SF-36)
Studies	1 study (Mutlu et al. 2020) - treatment subanalysis
Design	Cross-sectional with treatment subanalysis
Participants	N=17 initiated CPAP; 7 adherent \geq 1 month
Effect	Subjective improvement in adherent patients (quantitative data limited)
Risk of Bias	Serious (-1): Treatment subanalysis, no control, high attrition (7/17 adherent), selection bias, limited quantitative data
Inconsistency	Not downgraded (0): Only one study
Indirectness	Not downgraded (0): Direct population and intervention
Imprecision	Very Serious (-2): Very small sample (n=7 adherent), no quantitative estimates or CIs, subjective assessment only
Publication Bias	Not assessed: Too few studies
Overall Certainty	$\oplus\circ\circ\circ$ VERY LOW (Started at Low [observational], -1 risk of bias, -2 imprecision)

4.7 Summary of GRADE Certainty Across All Outcomes

Outcome	Studies (N)	Effect	Certainty	Reasons for Downgrading
Morning headache (CPAP)	1 (N=235)	81.3% improvement	$\oplus\oplus\circ\circ$ LOW	Risk of bias (-1), Imprecision (-1)
TMD pain (CPAP/MAD/Surgery)	1 (N=40)	Cohen's d = 0.8	$\oplus\oplus\circ\circ$ LOW	Risk of bias (-1), Indirectness (-1)
Primary headache (MAD)	1 (N=13)	62% \geq 30% reduction	$\oplus\circ\circ\circ$ VERY LOW	Risk of bias (-1), Imprecision (-2)
Generalized pain (CPAP)	1 (N=80)	Cohen's d = 1.2	$\oplus\oplus\circ\circ$ LOW	Risk of bias (-1), Indirectness (-1)
MS-related pain (CPAP)	1 RCT (N=34)	No difference (p=0.64)	$\oplus\oplus\oplus\circ$ MODERATE	Imprecision (-1)
Fibromyalgia pain (CPAP)	1 (N=7 adherent)	Subjective improvement	$\oplus\circ\circ\circ$ VERY LOW	Risk of bias (-1), Imprecision (-2)

Appendix 5: Extended Tables - Study Characteristics and Risk of Bias

5.1 Expanded Study Characteristics Table

Study	Country	Sample Details	OSA Details	Intervention Details	Outcome Assessment
Alessandri-Bonetti 2024	Italy	N=40; Age 51.3±10.3y; 77.5% male; BMI 26.5±3	Baseline AHI 21.9±13.1; Post-tx 8.4±4.7; PSG diagnosis	CPAP (n=8), MAD (n=9), Surgery (n=9), Combined (n=7); 83% completed	DC/TMD CPI scale; Baseline and 18 months
Khadadah 2022	Canada	N=34 completers (49 randomized); MS patients	Non-severe OSA (AHI 15-30); Excluded severe OSA	Fixed CPAP vs Sham CPAP; 6-month RCT; Double-blind	VAS pain; Baseline, 3 and 6 months
Mutlu 2020	Turkey	N=17 initiated CPAP (7 adherent ≥1 month); All female; Fibromyalgia	OSA by PSG; AHI not specified for treatment subgroup	CPAP; 7/17 adherent ≥1 month; Follow-up 1-3 months	SIQR, VAS, SF-36; Limited quantitative data
Nobre 2005	Brazil	N=37 cluster headache patients; 2 received CPAP	OSA documented in subgroup; PSG performed	CPAP in 2 patients; Immediate; Variable follow-up	Clinical assessment; Immediate improvement noted
Park 2021	Canada	N=13; Age 51±11y; 69% male; Primary headache with OSA	OSA diagnosed; Baseline AHI 19.0±10.6	MAD therapy; Mean follow-up 5.7 years (range 2-11 years)	MIDAS, VAS; Retrospective; Mean 3.9 assessments/patient
Shen 2023	China	N=80; Age 44.7±11.4y; 71.3% male; Chronic pain with OSA	Moderate-severe OSA; AHI ≥15; Mean AHI 42.5±21.8	CPAP; Adherent vs non-adherent; 3-month follow-up	SF-MPQ PRI, VAS, BPI; Baseline and 3 months
Suzuki 2015	Japan	N=235; Age 56.5±13.0y; 80% male; OSA with morning headache	OSA by PSG; AHI ≥5; Mean AHI 36.8±21.4	CPAP; ≥4h/night, ≥70% nights, ≥2 months; Mean 5.7±1.8 h/night	ICHD-3 beta criteria; Assessment at 2 months

5.2 Detailed Risk of Bias Summary Across All Domains

Study	Tool	Selection Bias	Performance Bias	Detection Bias	Attrition Bias	Reporting Bias	Overall
Alessandri-Bonetti 2024	NOS	Low (4/4 ★)	Moderate (1/2 ★)	Low	Low	Low	Low Risk
Khadadah 2022	RoB 2.0	Low	Low	Low	Some concerns (31% attrition)	Low	Low Risk
Mutlu 2020	NOS	Moderate	High (no control)	Moderate	High (59% attrition)	Low	High Risk
Nobre 2005	IHE	High	High (case series, n=2)	High	Moderate	Moderate	High Risk
Park 2021	NOS	Moderate	High (no control)	Moderate (retrospective)	Low	Low	Moderate Risk
Shen 2023	NOS	Low	Moderate (adherence comparison)	Low	Low	Low	Low Risk
Suzuki 2015	IHE	Moderate	High (no control)	Moderate	Low	Low	Moderate Risk

End of Supplementary Appendices
For questions or additional information, please contact the corresponding author.